

JOME MOSQUE IN THE ANCIENT KOKAN CITY

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Abstract. *The article is about one of the important links in our history - the unique feature of architecture. Bukhara, Samarkand, Ko'kan, Khiva, Tashkent and many other historical cities of our country are distinguished by their historical monuments, which gives infinite pride to the heart of a person. Among these, the topic we covered today is about the Jome Mosque, built during the reign of Amir Umarkhan in the city of Koqan, which is called "Latif shahar".*

Keywords: *Minglar clan, Kokand khanate, Umarkhan, jame mosque, muqarnas, Olimkhan, Mahmud Hakim Yaifani Khoqandi, Mulla Olim Makhdum Haji, Mirzo Olim Tashkandi, Khavaqand, Khoqand.*

Taking advantage of the political depression in the Emirate of Bukhara, which was ruled by the Ashtarkhanids, Chodak Khojas revolted and took control of the Ferghana Valley. But they cannot be independent . Shakhruhbi ibn Ashur Muhammad, a member of the Minglar clan, seized power from Chodak's lords and in 1709 established the rule of the Minglar dynasty in the Ferghana Valley. Thus, an independent state will emerge in the Fergana Valley with the city of Kokan as its center. At first, the heads of state ruled the country with the title of bey, not khan. After ascending to the throne in 1798, Olim Khan received the title of Uoziga Khan, and after that he ruled with the title of the head of the state until the end of the Kokan Khanate.

It is impossible not to dwell on the period of Umar Khan, the son of Norbotabi, who created a literary atmosphere in the Kokan Khanate and opened the way for women to engage in literature . Because he ruled the state with justice and won the love of people, he also received the title of Amir al-Mo'minin, that is, the Commander of the Faithful. The mosque and the madrasah, which are now the focus of tourists, were built during the reign of Umar Khan. The Jome Mosque, built at the beginning of the 19th century, forms a single ensemble with a well-kept courtyard. According to some reports , the mosque was built in the 18th century during the reign of Koqan Khan Amir Umar Khan (1809-1822). The people of the city performed Friday prayers in the mosque . It is said that the columns of Machit were sent from India by the poetess Zebunisa Begim (1639-1702), a descendant of Babur (in the 80s of the 20th century). The mosque was built as both a machit and a madrasah, and contained about a hundred rooms. The main facade of the building is facing east, with cornice patterns. The mosque is distinguished by its magnificent size (97.5X25.5) and variety of decorations. If the exterior bricks are left unpainted , the main facade and the interior are distinguished by their wealth of decorations. The lamps and beams of the ceiling are decorated with various patterns of Islamic and geometric shapes . The junction of the ceiling and the walls is decorated with muqarnas honors . The walls are richly decorated with right- angled panels . The inscriptions on the lower part of the walls are decorated with "chaspak". This type of decoration is characteristic of folk traditions and can be called a colorful crochet pattern. The technique of making it is not very complicated, but it is impressive. Some shapes are carved from ganch alloy and replaced with ganch of a different color. Then the wall surface is smoothed and finished. Decorating the interior of buildings in this style was used not only in the architecture of Ferghana, but also in other regions of Central Asia . the carved wooden columns of the mosque is finished with a skull muqarnas, and the bottom is

finished with a marble chair. This creates a reciprocal relationship with the material laid on the floor . According to the sources, the construction of Jome was started by Olimkhan (1801-1810 years). According to his decree , the place was chosen and the bricks were brought. But after Olimkhan was killed, the bricks were used to repair the Old Horde. Mahmud Hakim Yaifani Khoqandi writes about this:

"First, Amir Olimkhan repaired the Jame Mosque . When the building was built, the late teacher Muhammad Yaqub Akhun made the mahrasa of the building. Therefore, he donated all the goods and all the bricks to the Old Horde. Amir Jannatmakon also built the Jame Mosque in the same place after repairing it . According to Umar Khan's order, in 1817-1818, they built the Jami Mosque in the same place. Mulla Olim Makhdum Haji in his work " History of Turkestan" gives the following history dedicated to the construction of Jome:

"The owner of the world, Amir, is as bright as the sun,
He made those near and far happy.
The poor are happy with him,
The poor are happy with your charity.
Orphans do not remember their fathers,
All people are proud of their generosity.
Aliens forgot their homeland,
all relatives will benefit from the gift.
In his time, scientists are honorable,
Dear people were drowned in prayers .
They compiled the history of Jame' Mosque,
His donation is by the judgment of a prosperous ruler.
Its completion in two years,
This was one of the blessings of the sultan .
Consider the year of his history:
He said, "If you ask me, it's just Jome' Zuhur."

(Boz Jame' Zuhur) is the reason for the history, Olim Khan was going to build a Madrasa High building instead of the Jame Mosque, and after working on the wall to the height of a man, an obstacle stopped and Olim Khandin Umar Khan first demolished the building and built the Jame' Sharif Mosque and madrasa in its place for the second time. And also, because the society of Khoqand city became known and famous after the building of this Jame', the appearance of the Jame' has become history.

In Ibrat's "History of Ferghana" we can read the following sentences about the construction of Khomeini: "In the age of Umar Khan, it was important to build a madrasa, to develop science, and to introduce Sharia rules, and the Khan himself started When it is time to enter the building of the madrasa and lay the foundation stone, when all the scholars, fuzalo and umaros are gathered in Khokand province, is there anyone who has not had a mustahab happen to the person who laid the foundation stone since puberty? , when it was said that he was laying stones, none of these scholars and fuzalos were able, and when he was weak, the khan himself said: "Alhamdulillah, I have not done anything that is forbidden!" when he laid the foundation stone himself, the Ulemai asr ittifaq ilan gave him the nickname "Jannatmakon". Scholars, students and people of knowledge are flourishing in this heavenly age , and poetry is reliable.

The machit itself is fenced from three sides and is mounted on a pole as a domestic porch . The columns are made of such a hard type of wood that they are even called "stone wood". 10 of the columns are installed inside the room. Some of them have a plant-like carving pattern. The length of the machit is about 100 meters. It is slightly raised in the central part of the front . The ceiling of the machit is built in double-vassa style, in some places there are beams. The ceiling in front of the room is very beautiful and elegantly decorated.

In 1852, a minaret was built in front of Jome's mosque . The tower is in the form of a truncated cone, and the top ends with a six-sided cage - a hole and a dome . The majestic view of the 22-meter-high tower is unadorned, with a spiral staircase built into it .

In 1857, according to the decree of Khudoyor Khan, the mosque was provided . Mirza Olim Tashkandi writes about this in his work entitled " Ansab as -salatin wa tawarikhi al-havoqin": "And again, Umar Khan was in paradise during the time of Jame Mosque. When Mr. Khudoyar Khan went to the Friday prayer, I saw that the novgi (nugi) future was gone. Dafatan gathered the craftsmen together and left the owner, the foresight, and the foreman , and went on a jihad. Ersas two-year endowment has reached a thousand degrees higher than before..."

A lot of students studied in Jame' machit, it served the people very well . But during the colonial period , the building began to fall into disrepair due to lack of funds for repairs . The colors of the ornaments faded. Tsarist Russia did not provide funds for repairs . In such conditions, in 1906-1907, Mir Habib from Kokand decided to repair the building of this historical monument at his own expense. Masters from different cities and villages of Fergana valley started coming to Kokan. Masters even came from Armenia. However, along with the skilled and talented craftsmen, there were also young and experienced ones. In addition, it was necessary to use low-quality paints . But despite this, the repair work was completed and the rich people of Mir Habib expressed their gratitude.

As a result of the intensification of blasphemy during the former Union, Jome mosque and madrasa were closed. The cells were demolished , the porch of the mosque was covered with bricks, and the warehouse was also used as a flea market at some point. According to the request of the Kokan people, by the decision of the Kokan city executive committee, the mosque was renovated again in 1982 and returned to its original state. A modern survey for repairs found the original patterns and they were restored accordingly. But the most serious and timely work was the removal of the rotten lower part of the machit pillars and the installation of specially made stones of Jome church, a teahouse named "Guldasta" was built according to the projects of architects RAAhmedov and A.Ahmedov from Kokand . This building was built according to the traditions of Kokhan. Columns were skillfully worked by the famous engraver K. Haydarov . Another feature of the tea house is that it is decorated with very beautiful patterns intended for the elderly of Kokand. The walls are decorated with ganch. The more a person looks at the patterns , the more he is immersed in the illusion and does not notice the time has passed. We think it is worth mentioning the following about Machit's renovation work in 1982 . These repair works were carried out under the leadership of the chairman of the city executive committee, Shakirov. The reason why "Jome " is not written on the top of the machit is that atheism still had a lot of power in those years. The repair process was done with quick pictures . Because at this time, the movement to celebrate the thousandth anniversary of the city of Ko'kan was launched. " Khavokand" was written by mistake instead of the word "Jome" on the front of Machit .

However , the name of the city was not "Khavokand", but "Khoqand", and its age is more than two thousand years.

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